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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND *IN-VITRO* EVALUATION OF
MICONAZOLE BUCCAL PATCHES**Faizan Sayeed^{1*}, Rubeena Sultana², Syed Areefulla Hussainy³, and Abdul Sayeed⁴¹MESCO College of Pharmacy, Mustaidpura, Karwan Road, Hyderabad.

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Abstract:

The novel trans-buccoadhesive patches of Miconazole were prepared by solvent casting technique by employing the polymers of HPMC, Guar gum and Carbopol to obtain Miconazole buccal patches. The Miconazole buccal mucoadhesive patches were prepared by the method of solvent casting technique employing 'O' shape ring placed on a glass surface as substrate by using different polymers such as Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose - 15 cps (HPMC), Guar gum and Carbopol. Propylene glycol serves as the plasticizer as well as penetration enhancer. The prepared Miconazole mucoadhesive buccal patches were characterized based upon their physico-chemical characteristics like surface pH, swelling percentage, thickness, weight variation, hardness, Percentage Moisture Absorption and Percentage Moisture Loss, drug content and *In-vitro* drug release study was performed by using Modified Franz diffusion cell release studies. Based on the results of evaluation tests formulation coded Mf7 was concluded as best formulation. And the optimized formulation follows First order Higuchi's drug release mechanism.

Keywords: Miconazole, Buccal Patches, Solvent Casting Techniques**Corresponding author:****Faizan Sayeed,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Localized drug delivery to oral cavity tissues has been studied for the treatment of periodontal disease, bacterial infection, and fungal infection among the various routes of administration tried so far in the novel drug delivery systems. [1] Mucoadhesion has gained popularity over the years due to its potential to improve localized drug delivery by keeping a dosage form at the site of action (e. G. By keeping the formulation in close contact with the absorption site (e.G., within the gastrointestinal tract), the formulation can be administered systemically. G. Cavity in the mouth. A well-defined definition of bioadhesion [2] is a substance's propensity to stick for an extended period of time to biological tissues, whether it be synthetic or biological. The biological surface can be a mucous layer covering a tissue's surface or it can be epithelial tissue. Mucoadhesion is the term used to describe a phenomenon where adhesion is to a mucous coat. There are more applications for mucoadhesive polymers in buccal drug delivery. There are many mucoadhesive products that have recently been developed, including tablets, films, patches, disks, strips, ointments, and gels. But compared to other devices, buccal patches [3] offer more comfort and flexibility.

Advantages:

- It is richly vascularized and more accessible for administration and removal of dosage forms.
- High patient accessibility.
- An expanse of smooth muscle and relatively immobile mucosa, suitable for administration of retentive dosage forms.
- Direct access to systemic circulation through the internal jugular vein bypasses drugs from hepatic first pass metabolism, leading to high bioavailability.
- Bypass exposure of the drugs to the gastrointestinal fluids.
- More rapid cellular recovery and achievement of a localized site on smooth surface of buccal mucosa.
- Low enzyme activity, suitability for drugs/excipients that mildly and reversibly damages or irritates the mucosa.
- Non-invasive method of drug administration.
- Facility to include permeation enhancer or enzyme inhibitor or pH modifier in the formulation.

Disadvantages:

- Low permeability of buccal membrane.
- Small surface area (170 cm²).

- Subsequent dilution of the drug due to continuous secretion of saliva.
- Inconvenience of patients when eating or drinking.

Aim and objective of work:

The aim of the present study is to formulation development and invitro evaluations of oral mucoadhesive buccal patches of Miconazole with the following objectives.

- To study the drug and polymer interaction.
- To increase the bioavailability.
- To minimize the dose and reduce the side effects.
- Comparison of release profiles of different compositions of excipients in Miconazole buccal patches
- To improve the patient compliance.
- To study the drug and polymer interaction.

Preparation Of Linearity Plot Of Miconazole:**Preparation of phosphate buffer p^H 6.8**

Di-hydrogen phosphate 28.80 gm and potassium di-hydrogen phosphate 11.45 gm were dissolved in distilled water and volume was then made up to 1000 ml with distilled water.

Preparation of calibration curve:**Preparation of standard stock solution:**

10 mg Miconazole pure drug was taken into a 10ml standard flask and dissolved in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer. The volume of stock solution was made upto 10 ml with pH 6.8 phosphate buffer it gives 1000µg/ml concentration of Miconazole.

Preparation of working stock solution:

From the above stock solution, 1 ml was transferred into a 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was adjusted to 10 ml that corresponded to 100 µg/ml Miconazole in solution.

Preparation of working solution:

From that solution different aliquots of 0,2,0.4,0.6,0.8,1 ml were transferred to 10ml volumetric flask, volume was adjusted with pH 6.8 phosphate buffer, which gave a concentration of 2,4,6,8,10 µg/ml of final standard. Standard curve was plotted by taking absorbance of secondary stock solutions in UV double beam spectrophotometer at 224 nm.

FABRICATION OF MICONAZOLE BUCCAL PATCHES [4]:

The buccal mucoadhesive patches were prepared by the method of solvent casting technique⁵⁴⁻⁵⁶ using water as solvent. Employing 'O' shape ring placed on

a glass surface as substrate by using different polymers like Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose - 15 cps (HPMC), Guar gum and carbopol. Aqueous polymers of different concentrations were mixed in different ratios as mentioned.

Initially a solution of calculated quantities polymer was prepared by using absolute ethanol with occasional stirring for about 10 min. An accurately weighed 50 mg Miconazole was incorporated in polymeric solutions after levigation with 5% w/w propylene glycol which served the purpose of plasticizer as well as penetration enhancer. The solution was mixed occasionally to get semisolid

consistency. Then the solution was subjected to sonication in a bath sonicator to remove the air bubbles. Then this was casted on a glass surface employing 'O' shape ring covered with funnel to controlling the evaporation of solvent and allowed to dry at room temperature over night.

After careful examination, the dried patches were removed, checked for any imperfections or air bubbles and cut into 2 cm diameter patches using a specially fabricated circular stainless steel cutter. Then the formulations were stored in desiccators until further use.

Table No 1 : THE COMPOSITION OF BUCCAL PATCHES PREPARED USING MICONAZOLE

Formulation code	Polymers in mg			Solvents in ml		
	HPMC	Carbopol 934	Guar gum	PEG*(ml)	Ethanol	Water(ml)*
Mf1	200	-	-	2	10	40
Mf2	300	-	-	2	10	40
Mf3	-	200	-	2	10	40
Mf4	-	300	-	2	10	40
Mf5	-	-	200	2	10	40
Mf6	-	-	300	2	10	40
Mf7	300	200	-	2	10	40

Each patch (2*2cm²) contains 50mg of Miconazole.

Physico - chemical evaluation [5]:

Surface pH

Buccal Patches were left to swell for 2 h on the surface of an agar plate, prepared by dissolving 2 % (w/v) agar in warmed isotonic phosphate buffer of pH 6.8 under stirring and then pouring the solution into a petridish till gelling at room temperature. The surface pH was measured by means of a pH paper placed on the surface of the swollen patch. The mean of two reading was recorded.

Percentage moisture absorption (pma) [6]:

$$\text{Percentage Moisture Absorption} = \frac{\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

Percentage moisture loss (pml) [7]:

This test was also carried to check the integrity of Patches at dry condition. Three 1cm diameter Patches was cut out and weighed accurately and kept in desiccators containing fused anhydrous calcium chloride. After 72 hours the Patches were removed and weighed. Average percentage moisture loss of three Patches was found out.

$$\text{Percentage Moisture Loss} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

The percent moisture absorption test was carried out to check the physical stability of the buccal Patches at high humid conditions. In the present study the moisture absorption capacity of the Patches were determined as follows. Three 1cm diameter Patches were cut out and weighed accurately then the Patches were placed in desiccators containing saturated solution of aluminium chloride, keeping the humidity inside the desiccators at 79.5 %. After 3 days the Patches were removed, weighed and percentage moisture absorption was calculated. Average percentage moisture absorption of three Patches was found.

Swelling percentage (%s) :

A drug loaded Patches were placed in a thoroughly cleaned petridish having 50 ml of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer. An increase in the weight of the patch was noted in 15 min intervals for 60 min and the weight was calculated. The swelling percentage was calculated by using the following formula,

$$\% S = \frac{X_t - X_0}{X_0} \times 100$$

Where, % S - swelling percentage

X_t - the weight of swollen Patch after time t,

X_0 - weight of Patch at zero time.

Water vapour transmission rate (wvt) [8]:

For this study vials of equal diameter were used as transmission cells. These cells were washed thoroughly and dried in an oven. About 1 g of calcium chloride was taken in the cell and the polymeric Patches measuring 1 cm² area were fixed over the brim with the help of an adhesive. The cells were weighed accurately and initial weight was recorded, and then kept in a closed desiccators containing saturated solution of potassium chloride. The humidity inside the desiccators was found in between 80 – 90 % RH. The cells were taken out and weighed after 18, 36, 54 and 72 hrs.

From increase in weights the amount of water vapour transmitted and the rate at which water vapour transmitted were calculated by using the following formula.

$$W V T = WL/S$$

Where, W is water vapour transmitted in mg, L is thickness of the Patch in mm, S is exposed surface area in cm².

Thickness:

The thickness of each Patches was measured by using a digital vernier caliper at six different positions of the Patch and the average thickness was calculated.

Weight of patches:

The weights of three Patches were taken and the weight variation was calculated.

Folding endurance:

Folding endurance of the Patch was determined by repeatedly folding one patch at the same place till it broke or folded upto 300 times manually, which was considered satisfactory to reveal good Patch properties. The number of times of Patch could be folded at the same place without breaking gave the value of the folding endurance. This test was done for three Patches.

Drug content estimation [9]:

A Patch was cut into three pieces of equal diameter were taken in separate 100 ml of pH 6.8 phosphate

buffer was added and continuously stirred for 24 h. The solutions were filtered, suitably diluted and analyzed at 248 nm in a UV Spectro photometer. The average of drug content of three Patches was taken as final reading.

Bioadhesion test:

The fresh sheep mouth separated and washed with phosphate buffer (pH 6.8). A piece of gingival mucosa is tied in the open mouth of a glass vial, filled with phosphate buffer (pH 6.8). This glass vial is tightly fitted into a glass beaker filled with phosphate buffer (pH 6.8, 37°C ± 1°C) so it just touched the mucosal surface. The patch is stuck to the lower side of a rubber stopper with cyano acrylate adhesive. Two pans of the balance are balanced with a 5-g weight. The 5-g weight is removed from the left hand side pan, which loaded the pan attached with the patch over the mucosa. The balance is kept in this position for 5 minutes of contact time.

The water is added slowly at 100 drops/min to the right-hand side pan until the patch detached from the mucosal surface. The weight, in grams, required to detach the patch from the mucosal surface provided the measure of mucoadhesive strength.

Invitro drug diffusion studies [10]:

In-vitro drug release study was performed by using Modified Franz diffusion cell on egg membrane in phosphate buffer solution (pH 6.8). Egg membrane was mounted horizontally on the receptor compartment of Franz diffusion cell. The effective permeation area of donor compartment exposed to receptor compartment was 2cm² and capacity of receptor compartment was 250ml of phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) maintained at 37± 0.5°C and stirred by a magnetic bar at 100rpm. Miconazole buccal patch formulation equivalent to 50mg drug was placed on the skin and the top of the diffusion cell was covered. At appropriate time intervals 5 ml aliquots of the receptor medium were withdrawn at predetermined time intervals for all the batches and immediately replaced by an equal volume of fresh phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) to maintain sink conditions. A ten-

fold dilution of each of the withdrawn sample was made and the diluted solutions were thereafter analyzed spectrophotometrically at 224 nm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Preparation of calibration curve:

The standard graph of Miconazole linearity with R^2 of 0.998, and the equation of graph is $y=0.079x - 0.002$, which suggests that it obeys the "Beer-Lambert's law".

Table No 2: Standard plot of Miconazole in 6.8 pH phosphate buffer

CONCENTRATION ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	ABSORBANCE at 224nm
0	0
2	0.165 \pm 0.21
4	0.311 \pm 0.17
6	0.467 \pm 0.11
8	0.615 \pm 0.08
10	0.809 \pm 0.16

Drug excipient compatibility study :

Compatibility studies were performed using FTIR spectrophotometer. The FTIR spectrum of pure drug and physical mixture of drug and other excipients were studied. The correlation between the pure drug and excipients indicated that the drug was compatible with the formulation excipients.

Fig. 3: FTIR spectra of Miconazole pure drug FTIR

Fig. 4: FTIR spectra of Miconazole Optimized formulation

FTIR studies were performed to understand the compatibilities between the drug with different excipients. The figures above illustrate that the functional groups like C–H stretching with the observation range of 3000-2500 has peaks at 2971.69 in pure drug and 2938.00 in optimized formulation. Similarly the functional group C–Cl stretching has a peak range of 850-550 has peaks at 631.55 in pure drug and 641.66 in optimized formulation. The functional groups in both the pure drug and optimized formulation are found. Hence it can be concluded that the pure drug is compatible with the excipients used in the study.

Table No. 3 : Physicochemical evaluation of buccal patches of Miconazole

Formulation Code	Surface pH ± SD	PMA ± SD	PML ± SD	Swelling Index ± SD	WTR ± SD	Thickness (mm) ± SD	Weight of patches in mg ± SD	Drug Content in mg	Folding endurance
Mf1	6.4±0.005	8.21±0.07	10.24±0.12	72.4±1.04	10.18±0.35	0.44±0.01	160.72±1.24	86.78	171
Mf2	6.5±0.005	9.38±0.04	9.49±0.54	87.67±0.27	7.67±0.34	0.41±0.01	171.97±0.8	89.29	165
Mf3	6.1±0.012	10.21±0.09	8.54±0.1	92.4±0.38	7.17±0.34	0.43±0.01	160.74±0.52	92.36	167
Mf4	6.6±0.005	14.06±0.19	7.21±0.64	106.7±0.41	5.92±0.08	0.42±0.01	162.48±0.18	94.72	178
Mf5	6.7±0.015	15.13±0.09	5.32±0.03	101.31±0.19	5.98±0.08	0.41±0.02	171.37±0.65	87.06	198
Mf6	6.8±0.04	14.1±0.06	6.61±0.2	104±0.28	5.39±0.32	0.44±0.02	173.15±1.06	91.42	188
Mf7	6.8±0.08	17.45±0.04	11.18±0.4	116.14±0.48	4.4±0.35	0.41±0.01	174.18±1.04	97.58	221

Measurement of Buccoadhesive Strength:

The bioadhesive strength exhibited by Miconazole buccal patches was satisfactory for maintaining them in oral cavity. The formulation Mf7 with HPMC and Carbopol shows good adhesion. The highest Buccoadhesive strength was found to be in formulation Mf7.

Fig.5 : Buccoadhesive Strength of Formulations Mf1 to Mf7

Table No.4 :*IN-VITRO* Diffusion Drug Release Data For Miconazole Buccal Patches

Time in hrs	Mf1	Mf2	Mf3	Mf4	Mf5	Mf6	Mf7
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30min	9.16±0.89	5.13±0.31	9.65±0.53	10.24±0.32	6.19±0.49	8.42±0.43	13.49±0.51
1	12.34±0.23	10.24±0.54	15.42±0.92	17.15±0.76	12.34±0.46	17.28±0.95	21.02±0.62
2	21.68±0.19	18.35±0.76	24.35±0.86	28.16±0.43	19.42±0.42	28.21±0.27	39.93±0.92
3	32.26±0.28	26.45±0.23	36.62±0.45	39.58±0.76	28.34±0.71	35.27±0.39	52.27±0.76
4	37.15±0.35	36.26±0.59	42.35±0.62	48.29±0.31	34.46±0.39	46.15±0.92	64.19±0.89
5	40.57±0.21	48.38±0.087	49.26±0.53	61.37±0.48	42.26±0.82	58.34±0.73	69.41±0.54
6	47.88±0.62	60.12±0.39	58.34±0.59	74.61±0.43	51.8±0.69	65.12±0.54	76.23±0.29
7	59.18±0.49	68.34±0.27	72.24±0.91	82.46±0.59	55.64±0.32	69.24±0.64	85.41±0.45
8	72.42±0.31	79.19±0.81	80.02±0.76	86.16±0.51	59.42±0.46	74.15±0.43	94.62±0.32

Fig.6:INVITRO DIFFUSION RELEASE FOR FORMULATION Mf1-Mf4

Fig.7 :In-vitro Diffusion Release For Formulation Mf5-Mf7

Table No.5 :KINETIC STUDIES FOR OPTIMIZED FORMULATION

	ZERO	FIRST	HIGUCHI	PEPPAS
	% CDR Vs T	Log % Remain Vs T	%CDR Vs \sqrt{T}	Log C Vs Log T
Slope	11.075012	-0.12684809	34.466095	1.08054835
Intercept	11.057001	2.03682266	-7.1727732	1.05516255
R 2	0.9576135	0.96242379	0.9861147	0.55650813

DISCUSSION:

The Miconazole buccal mucoadhesive patches were prepared by the method of solvent casting technique employing 'O' shape ring placed on a glass surface as

substrate by using different polymers such as Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose - 15 cps (HPMC), Guar gum and Carbopol. Propylene glycol serves as a plasticizer as well as penetration enhancer.

Drug polymer compatibility studies were performed by FTIR (Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy). The prepared Miconazole buccal patches were characterized based upon their physico chemical characteristics like surface pH, PMA, PML, swelling percentage, WVT, thickness, weight, folding endurance and drug content as shown in the above table.

The *in-vitro* drug release studies were performed as the release of the drug from the dosage form plays an important role in buccal drug delivery and in determining the therapeutic effect of the drug. The *in-vitro* drug release studies were performed by using a modified dissolution apparatus with donor-receptor compartments.

Drug –polymer compatibility studies by FTIR:

The FTIR spectra of Miconazole, HPMC, Guar gum, Carbopol and the combination of drug and polymers showed no significant interaction between drug and polymer. The FTIR spectra of Miconazole, HPMC, Guar gum, Carbopol mixture of drug along with polymers are shown in figure.

Surface Ph:

Because acidic or alkaline pH may cause irritation to the buccal mucosa and influence the rate of hydration of the polymers, the surface pH of the patches was determined. The observed surface pH of the formulations was found to be in the range of 6.1 ± 0.02 to 6.8 ± 0.01 . The results are found that there is no significant difference of surface pH in all the formulations and the pH range lies within the range of salivary pH i.e. 6.5 to 6.8, hence does not cause irritation and achieve patient compliance. Surface pH values of all the formulations are represented in the table.

Percentage Moisture Absorption and Percentage Moisture Loss:

Checking the physical stability of the patch at high humid conditions and integrity of the patch at dry conditions, the patches were evaluated for PMA and PML. The observed results of PMA and PML were shown in the tabular column. The percentage Moisture uptake in the formulation Mf7 has shown the highest value of moisture absorption 17.45 ± 0.04 . The formulation Mf5 shows higher value of Moisture loss.

Swelling percentage:

The above table shows the swelling percentage of the formulated buccal patches. The swelling behaviour of the polymer was reported to be crucial for its

bioadhesive character. The adhesion occurs shortly after swelling but the bond formed is not very strong. The adhesion increases with the degree of hydration till the point of disentanglement at the polymer tissue surface, which leads to abrupt drop in adhesive strength due to over hydration.

The formulation Mf7 shows higher value of Swelling percentage 116.14 ± 0.48 .

Water Vapour Transmission:

Water vapor transmission rate through various patches were shown above. Water vapor transmission studies indicated that all the patches were permeable to water vapour. The formulation Mf7 has shown maximum water vapor transmission of among all the patches.

Thickness and Weight of patches:

The patch thicknesses were observed by using digital vernier caliper and found to be in the range of 0.41 ± 0.01 mm to 0.44 ± 0.01 mm. The weight of the patches was found to be in the range of 160.72 ± 1.24 mg to 174.18 ± 1.04 mg.

Drug content estimation:

The observed results of content uniformity indicated that the drug was uniformly dispersed and with minimum intra batch variability. Recovery was possible to the tune of 86.78 to 97.58.

Measurement of Bucco adhesive Strength:

The muco adhesive properties of the fabricated patches were shown in table 5.2. The bioadhesive strength exhibited by Miconazole buccal patches was satisfactory for maintaining them in oral cavities. The formulation Mf7 with HPMC and Carbopol shows good adhesion. The highest Bucco adhesive strength was found to be in formulation Mf7.

***In-vitro* drug release studies:**

Distinguishable difference was observed in the release of Miconazole in all formulations. The results and data of *in vitro* studies are shown in the table. Formulations Mf1, Mf2 containing HPMC 0.5%, 0.75% they gave a reasonable Miconazole release up to 8 h.

- Formulations, Mf3 and Mf4 containing Carbopol 934 0.5%, 0.75%, Mf5 and Mf6 containing Guar gum 0.5%, 0.75% respectively gave a reasonable Miconazole release up to 8 h.
- The formulations Mf1, Mf2, Mf3, Mf4, Mf5, Mf6 and Mf7 has shown release 72.42%, 79.19%, 80.02%, 86.16%, 59.42%, 74.15%, and 94.62% respectively. Formulations Mf7 containing Combination of HPMC,

Carbopol gave a reasonable Miconazole release up to 8 h.

CONCLUSION:

- The prepared Miconazole mucoadhesive buccal patches were characterized based upon their physico-chemical characteristics like surface pH, swelling percentage, thickness, weight variation, hardness, Percentage Moisture Absorption and Percentage Moisture Loss, drug content and *in-vitro* release studies,
- *In-vitro* drug release study was performed by using Modified Franz diffusion cell. The formulations Mf1, Mf2, Mf3, Mf4, Mf5, Mf6 and Mf7 has shown release 72.42%, 79.19%, 80.02%, 86.16%, 59.42%, 74.15%, and 94.62% respectively. Formulations Mf7 containing Combination of HPMC, Carbopol gave a reasonable Miconazole release up to 8 h. From the above results Mf7 (94.62%) was considered as optimized formulation.
- The drug release from formulation Mf7 was explained by first order kinetics as the plot showed highest linearity ($r^2=0.962$), as the drug release was best fitted in first order kinetics, it indicates that the rate of drug release is dependent of its concentration.
- The optimized formulation follows first order and Higuchi's release mechanism of drug release.

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